

MODERN APPROACHES TO USE A MOBILE PHONE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS

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The most important task of teaching English in a national school is the development of coherent speech of students, which is due to the principle of communicative orientation of education. The solution of communicative tasks should lead to the fact that the graduates of the national school have a good command of their native and English languages. Today, it is difficult to imagine a lesson without modern pedagogical technologies. Modern approaches to a mobile phone in foreign language lessons. The mobile phone has become an indispensable attribute in the life of any modern person. Currently, teenagers practically do not part with this fashionable gadget. They use it not only as a means of communication with friends, loved ones, but also for other purposes. Many mobile devices of the latest generation can act as a calculator, flashlight, video camera, voice recorder, audio player, video player, camera, and finally have access to the Internet. In this regard, modern children are showing increased interest in mobile phones, namely, in the opportunities that these devices open up for them. No wonder many people call these gadgets smartphones. The word "smartphone" comes from two English words: "smart", which is translated into Russian as "smart", and "phone", which is translated into Russian as "telephone". Thanks to the knowledge of the Russian translation of the word "smartphone", we can say with confidence that the role of this gadget in people's lives is not at all exaggerated. Certainly, mobile phones can bring many benefits to children if they are used wisely. But, on the other hand, they also have a negative impact on adolescents. The constant excessive use of mobile devices leads to the fact that children and adolescents may develop computer addiction. Many teachers notice that students even in the classroom are enthusiastically looking at the screens of smartphones, not listening to the teacher's explanations. First of all, the quality of education suffers from this. Children suffering from such dependence on mobile phones are more likely to get tired, irritated, protest at the requests of the teacher, parents, classmates, perform tasks in the classroom poorly. Given the fact that English is one of the most difficult disciplines in the curriculum, the teacher needs to make sure that mobile devices are not the worst enemies of the process of transferring and acquiring new knowledge, but, on the contrary, become excellent allies in these

matters. As an English teacher in a secondary school, I noticed that students of middle and senior school age often use phones in class. Children are distracted from the educational process, "sitting" in social networks, neglecting to receive important information in the classroom. I can say that it is in the power of a foreign language teacher to change the situation for the better when students start using these trendy gadgets for educational purposes. The main goal of teaching a foreign language at school is the formation of the communicative competence of students. It is possible to realize this goal through the systematic use of various new educational technologies, techniques and methods of teaching a foreign language, improving the skills of various types of speech activity of schoolchildren (in reading, listening, writing, vocabulary and grammar, speaking). In my English lessons, I use my mobile phone effectively. For example, the audio player function of this gadget turned out to be very useful. When preparing a lesson at home, using the Internet, I download audio recordings with English speech on the topic of the lesson in mp3 format to my mobile phone, at the lesson I connect my gadget to the speakers, thereby making listening to the audio recording available to all participants in the educational process. At the end of the lesson, students download this audio recording to their mobile phones. Thanks to the presence of an audio player function in modern phones, children can listen to audio recordings in English at home instead of modern music. This is very handy: a mobile device is always at hand for a modern teenager and is more compact than a tape recorder, a computer. For those children who do not have such an opportunity to transfer the educational audio file to their gadget, a way out of this situation is provided, namely, I send educational material on the topic of the lesson to the personal email address of such students. In order to avoid confusion with the electronic addresses of schoolchildren, any teacher for a particular class can independently create a single email, give students a password from it. The teacher has the ability to send all the necessary files that are useful to children in learning English to this single e-mail of the class. Similar actions can be taken by the teacher regarding the use of English instructional videos. Many smartphones perform the function of a video player. Educational video files in English offered by the teacher can be downloaded by students to their mobile phones and used for viewing at a convenient time for children. For students in grades 2-11, I often create interactive tasks in English for repetition and consolidation of lexical, grammatical, linguistic and cultural material. These interactive exercises are created by me using a service called "LearningApps.org". Students in the lesson can be given information about a link to a particular interactive task, and they

will begin to complete it. Children can also complete these tasks at home using their mobile devices that have access to the Internet. I also want to admit that my students take pictures of everything they need to learn English, they look into electronic dictionaries in search of the meaning of foreign words, thanks to the functions of their mobile devices. It is worth noting that some electronic dictionaries in English are limited in terms of vocabulary, so I recommended that my students use online dictionaries on the site www.multitran.ru. At home, the guys, having resorted to the help of their gadgets, can also visit educational sites to learn English, receiving the necessary information. Today's children have a completely different way of life. Every minute is used by them as useful as possible, because there is so much new information around, so much the guys need to do, and a lot has to be done on the go. Therefore, a mobile phone can be considered a means not only for communication, but also for learning. In many cases, mobile devices are more of a hindrance in the classroom than a help. Therefore, it is important for the teacher to teach the children to use them in the classroom and at home with maximum benefit and for their intended purpose.

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